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WIND IN MY BACKYARD

WIMBY

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SHORT ABSTRACT FOR DISSEMINATION PURPOSES

Abstract

This deliverable 4.4 "*Report on stakeholder mapping and best practices for project implementation*" provides a comprehensive approach to identify, and categorize stakeholders based on their level of influence and interest, and assess their attitudes toward wind power deployment.

A systematic approach developed from best practice of practitioners helps to understand stakeholders' perceptions, concerns and potential objections related to wind projects. Following the principles of network analysis, a cluster analysis sheds light on the project-specific stakeholders, specifically their characteristics and attitudes towards project implementation and their respective relation to each other within two WIMBY pilots. Compensatory measures to mitigate antagonising local stakeholders of wind projects, increase their acceptance, and gain their support for wind energy initiatives are explored.

The three respective steps implemented are: a) data collection on the basis of desk-based literature research; b) semi-structured interviews with the main stakeholders conducted at two WIMBY pilot sites, i.e., Pantelleria (IT) and Styria (A); and c) network analysis based on a comprehensive digest of the semi-structured interviews.

The report includes a manual for the methodological approach, backed by the comprehensive analysis of semi-structured interviews conducted at the WIMBY pilot sites in Pantelleria and Styria.

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ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym	Description
WT	Wind Turbine
SRI	Standford Research Institute
CSR	Corporate Social Responsibility
ESG	Environmental, Social, and Governance
SNA	Social Network Analysis
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
mu	Municipality
ps	Power Suppliers
lo	Land owner
np	National Park
en	Entrepreneurs
to	Tourism association
ag	Agricultural
sch	Schools
me	Media
re	Residents
pd	Project developer
mul	Municipality Irdning
muE	Municipality Ennstal
ag&f	Agricultural & Forestry
rgov	Regional Government
rel	Religious Entities
IDS	Identifiers
IBA	Important Bird and Biodiversity Areas
ÖVP	Österreichische Volkspartei
GEFA	Gemeinsam für Aigen
SPÖ	Sozialdemokratische Partei Österreichs
FPÖ	Freiheitliche Partei Österreichs

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

An effective stakeholder engagement strategy enhances trust, transparency, and open communication with actors facilitating project implementation. Wind power has great potential to underpin clean energy targets but opposition from different stakeholders has and will continue to delay or even hinder its deployment. Task T4.3 (resulting in this D4.4) addresses the concerns of stakeholders to increase acceptance of wind energy with its objective being to design and develop a standard approach for stakeholder engagement based on best practices from practitioners and experts in the field. The report has the form of a manual for stakeholder management.

To develop this approach, two WIMBY pilot sites, i.e., Pantelleria (IT) and Styria (A) were selected to gather information from different socio-cultural contexts. Two workshops at European University Viadrina with practitioners of stakeholder engagement and experts in dialogue creation and participatory approaches developed a methodology and strategic approach to identify stakeholders and their concerns, to be able to address them with the aim to increase acceptance for project implementation. Based on this methodology 44 semi-structured interviews were carried out with relevant stakeholders in Styria (22) and Pantelleria (22), with the following key objectives:

- Verify the identification, mapping and clustering of all relevant stakeholders.
- Following the principles of network analysis to devise a cluster analysis to shed light on the project-specific stakeholders, specifically their characteristics and attitudes towards project implementation and their respective relation to each other.
- Address the concerns of stakeholders who are in opposition to wind power projects and gain their support.
- Explore compensatory measures to mitigate antagonising local stakeholders of wind projects, increase their acceptance and gain their support for wind energy initiatives.

The main results of this D4.3 include a methodological framework for stakeholder analysis and engagement, and – applying this methodology – a preliminary network analysis for the pilot sites of Pantelleria (IT) and Styria (A).

Instead of economic experiments we devised semi-structured interviews and network analysis to approach the question of attitude formation. This deviation had two reasons: a) the expert and practitioner feedback from the two preparatory workshops indicated the network analysis approach as more appropriate; b) semi-structured interviews were much more suitable to accommodate time and resource constraints and the limited availability of local stakeholders during the pilot visits. Thanks to the adaptation of the approach described above, all related task objectives were achieved.

The network analysis was undertaken to map and understand the relationships, roles, and levels of influence among the stakeholders involved in the (hypothetical) wind energy project. This method allows us to capture the complexity of interactions within the network, identify key actors, and analyse how their positions and connections influence the project's progress. Through this process, stakeholders were categorized into three main groups—core stakeholders, expanded stakeholders, and multipliers—based on their degree of involvement, influence, and alignment with the project's objectives. This categorization not only highlights the distinct roles each group plays but also provides valuable insights for developing targeted engagement strategies to enhance collaboration and ensure the project's success.

Our network analysis of Pantelleria and Styria underlines the importance of individuals on a wind energy project's success and the variety of key actors, depending on the region. While in Pantelleria people affiliated with the national park and the media play a significant role in opinion-shaping, in Styria it is renewable energy pioneers who influence public opinion.

1. Introduction, Objective and Context

Wind energy is gaining significant momentum in global geopolitics to secure energy independence and reduce CO₂ emissions. The rapid deployment of onshore and offshore wind turbines raises issues of social acceptance of wind energy (Gartmann, Victoria et al., 2014) including understanding the perceptions of the various actors involved in wind energy deployment. Ignoring the concerns of key actors may delay the installation of wind turbines or even lead to the failure of projects (LaPatin et al., 2022). Against this background, stakeholder engagement is a crucial step for identifying, addressing, and mitigating objections and or concerns of the various actors. This step not only ensures transparency and mutual trust among the various project actors but also enhances social acceptance of wind projects across affected communities (Schuldis, 2019). However, opposition against wind power deployment from the local communities in Europe threatens to derail reaching the clean energy targets. In order to provide science-based information and raise awareness in society, WIMBY aims to engage citizens to gain support for wind projects.

This manual aims to present the best practices for stakeholder engagement for the successful execution of wind power deployment based on best practice of experts and practitioners in the field. To develop this approach, we selected two WIMBY pilot sites, i.e., Pantelleria (IT) and Styria (A) to gather information from different socio-cultural contexts, identify stakeholders, and address their concerns. Following two workshops at European University Viadrina with stakeholder engagement practitioners and experts in dialogue creation and participatory approaches our team developed a methodology and strategic approach for stakeholder engagement with the aim to increase acceptance for project implementation. This approach is based on engaging and interviewing key stakeholder groups to map out dynamics and relations between them regarding support and/or protest against a (at this point hypothetical) wind project.⁴

⁴ Instead of economic experiments we devised semi-structured interviews and network analysis. This deviation resulted from: a) expert and practitioner feedback from the two workshops indicating the network analysis approach as more appropriate; and b) the fact that semi-structured interviews were more suitable to accommodate time and resource constraints as well as limited availability of local stakeholders during the pilot visits.

Accordingly, and based on this methodology 44 semi-structured interviews were carried out with all relevant stakeholders in Styria (22) and Pantelleria (22) with the following key objectives:

- Verify the identification, mapping and clustering of all relevant stakeholders.
- Following the principles of network analysis to devise a cluster analysis to shed light on the project-specific stakeholders, specifically their characteristics and attitudes towards project implementation and their respective relation to each other.
- Address the concerns of stakeholders who are in opposition to wind power projects and gain their support.
- Explore compensatory measures to mitigate antagonising local stakeholders of wind projects, increase their acceptance and gain their support for wind energy initiatives.

1.1 The Stakeholder Concept

The “*stakeholder concept*” was coined by Standford Research Institute’s (SRI) memo in 1963 to acknowledge that businesses have a wider range of societal responsibilities beyond their shareholder’s interest (Freeman, 2004). The SRI memo defines stakeholders as “*those groups without whose support the organization would cease to exist*” clearly identifying those stakeholders who have power, can influence, and have a legitimate association with the project developer, and thereby can actively change the project trajectory or business strategy (Freeman and McVea, 2005). Under a conventional approach (Freeman et al., 2021), a company is obliged to fiduciary duty towards its shareholders to generate more profit. Appeasing investors and shareholders by generating more profit might be beneficial for the company in the short term but this strategy can derail the company’s long-term sustainability. Investors may be sceptical about investing in companies who only consider the interests of their shareholders and neglect responsibilities towards society and the environment. Against the backdrop of the rising threat of climate change, it is crucial to consider morale and ethics towards creating value for society rather than merely generating profit for their shareholders.

The “*stakeholder concept*” evolved over the years through the embodiment of corporate planning, system theory, corporate social responsibility (CSR), and organization theory into “*stakeholder management*” with its definitions

being extended in the literature. In 2004 a United Nations report entitled “Who Cares Wins” introduced an Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) framework that considers the impact of a company’s operations on society and the environment (Eccles, 2022). Companies that have high ESG scores enjoy higher growth than their peers (Doherty et al., 2023). The inclusion of broader stakeholders in the project not only mitigates the risk in the long run but also devises a strategy for the success of the project. Extending the definition (Mitchell et al., 1997) to entities or communities that do not have a legitimate association with the project developer embraces stakeholders, for instance, a neighbouring community being affected by wind turbines installed in its vicinity. If project developers do not consider the concerns of the local population during the planning phase of a wind power project, it may cause severe problems during project implementation. Hence, the definition must include both those who can influence and those that are affected by the project. Consequently, Freeman and McVea (2005) break with the conventional shareholder-centric approach by defining stakeholders beyond economic advantage as *“any group or individual who is affected by or can affect the achievement of an organization’s objectives.”*

1.2 Stakeholder Theory and its Different Layers

In the literature stakeholder theory embraces organizational management and business ethics that addresses a business relationships and responsibilities with various entities that affect or are affected by its actions (Parmar et al., 2010). Such theories suggest that the success of the company relies on stakeholders not merely on shareholders. Stakeholder theories can be categorised into (i) descriptive, (ii) instrumental, and (iii) normative (Donaldson and Preston, 1995).

- Descriptive theory (Donaldson and Preston, 1995) shows the corporate characteristics and reality of the situation of stakeholders. It illustrates the factual relationship and interaction of the firm with stakeholders without making any judgment. For instance, the Wind power operator RWE is associated with stakeholders such as investors, employees, wind turbine manufacturers, regulators, municipalities, etc.
- Instrumental theory (Freeman, 2010) goes one step further by linking stakeholder consideration to a company’s objective. The close association and consideration of stakeholders help project developers devise

a constructive strategy that mutually benefits all the partners regarding financial growth and the project objective. When project developers involve stakeholders in formulating the overall strategy, stakeholders possibly enjoy economic benefits which contributes to embedding trust among them.

- A normative theory (Donaldson and Preston, 1995) illustrates business ethics and moral on how a company treats its partners or stakeholders. It mainly includes accountability, transparency, moral and philosophical guidelines, and environmental stewardship. Transferred to wind power deployment this means that wind power developers should engage in open and transparent communication with all relevant local stakeholder groups while being accountable for the social and environmental impacts of their projects actively seeking to minimize any negative effects. This involves conducting a thorough environmental assessment, involving the local community in the siting and planning process, and ensuring that also the benefits of wind power are equitably shared. These claims are backed by the finding that proactive engagement with stakeholders leads to more informed decision-making and increased project acceptance (Cowell et al., 2011).

The above three stakeholder theories are structured hierarchically with each theory encompassing different aspects of stakeholder engagement. At the outermost layer, descriptive theory captures the observed reality of stakeholder relationships providing an empirical account of how firms interact with various stakeholders. Closer to project implementation is instrumental theory emphasising the strategic alignment and close collaboration among stakeholders to achieve a wind project's objectives. At the core lies normative theory underscoring the intrinsic value and moral obligations that firms have towards their stakeholders highlighting the ethical considerations that should guide stakeholder interactions (Donaldson and Preston, 1995). Organisations pursuing an instrumental theory to achieve merely financial goals can gain substantial economic advantages in the short term, but their business may not be sustainable in the long term. Combining descriptive, instrumental, and normative theory provides a holistic approach to meet stakeholder expectations, adhering to societal norms while facilitating their acceptance of wind power projects.

2. From Stakeholder Mapping to Stakeholder Engagement

The initial phase to develop a coherent stakeholder engagement strategy is to map all stakeholders possibly relevant for project implementation, which is a preparatory on-the-desk research task (see Section 2.1 below). Following the mapping of stakeholders according to the above stakeholder theories the next more complex step is not only to assess the interrelations of various actors with the company, in our case a wind project developer, but also to develop a strategy to understand the interaction among these actors. This is crucial to maintaining healthy relations between them and underpin corporate strategy (see Section 2.2 below). In the corporate world different methods for what is dubbed "stakeholder management" are underpinned by three levels of analysis unravelling the complexities of stakeholder relations at the levels of rationale, process, and transaction (Freeman, 2010).

The first step is identifying the stakeholders and perceived stakes in the organisation. Subsequently, a deep understanding of organisational and decision-making processes connecting stakeholders implicitly or explicitly helps to identify the characteristics of relationships (mono-directional, reciprocal) and content (ethical, commercial, personal, etc.) of their relations. This comprehension aids in recognizing the motivations, interests, and influences of the various stakeholders. In a third step, we explore possible compensatory offers which may include both sharing financial benefits and participation in decision-making in order to overcome scepticism and/or protest against a wind power project (see Section 2.2 below).

Before describing stakeholder engagement in more detail, it is necessary to underscore some key questions guiding stakeholder management and delineate the term vis-a-vis stakeholder engagement. Key questions of both concepts are:

- What is the mission or objective of the organisation driving the project, here the wind project developer?
- What resource allocation or budgets must be made for the strategies to be implemented?
- Who are those groups and individuals that can affect and are affected by the achievement of an organisation/project purpose?

Since the approach developed for WIMBY centres around the idea of participatory engagement in order to increase local acceptance and support, we

depart from the "top-down" idea of "stakeholder management" assuming a certain passivity of the stakeholders and implying that they can be managed by a third party. WIMBY's approach in contrast is based on the idea of "stakeholder engagement" aiming - where possible and feasible - at an active involvement of local stakeholders and a resulting co-creation process (Loureiro et al., 2020). To do so, we designed our stakeholder engagement framework with the help of experts possessing expertise from ample practical experience with project implementation (Michael Krieger, a qualified expert in participatory approaches and dialogue creation within the energy transition). Two five-day intensive workshops were organised, entitled a) "How to build a wind park" and b) "Wind Power project deployment against the background of Stakeholder Engagement". Both were held at the European Viadrina University Frankfurt (Oder) together with experts and students⁵. Two pilot sites, i.e., Pantelleria (IT) and Syria (A) were selected for the workshops to compare the methodological approach with the real-world situation in order to develop a general stakeholder engagement approach that can be used as a standard method for wind power deployment.

2.1 Overview of the Approach and the Subsequent Steps

Our methodological framework offers a structured approach to identifying and addressing stakeholder positions to ensure effective engagement and increase acceptance of wind energy projects (see Figure 1). The first step under this framework is a **Stakeholder Mapping** identifying all parties affected by or influential to the project. Desk-based research was carried out to understand the socio-demographic factors to assess the characteristics, behaviours, and needs of different stakeholder groups. This step allows to cover stakeholders across three categories i.e. core stakeholders, expanded core of stakeholders, and multipliers. Additionally, a proportionate sample is included within each category to ensure preciseness and accuracy in further steps.

The **Stakeholder Analysis: Part I** assesses the **abstract position** of the stakeholder using eight interview questions based on four dimensions namely environment, society, economy, and culture. The initial analysis helps to shape engagement strategies that directly address stakeholder

⁵ A total of ten students participated both seminars, divided into five groups with two students in each group. An Interactive Miro board was set up to ensure the participation of all the students and test the methodological approach from different students' views.

concerns. Better specificity of the project is undertaken after understanding the initial position of the stakeholders. The **Stakeholder Analysis: Part II** addresses the specificity of the project using four interview questions focussed on the project. This step uncovers the stakeholder’s **concrete perception** of the project regarding knowledge, information, emotions, and participation. In a subsequent fourth step a **Tendency Analysis** determines the degree of congruency between Part I and Part II. If the stakeholder position from the analysis and engagement part is congruent an informative approach for transparent information sharing to reinforce support for the project is chosen. Similarly, if the tendencies from analysis and engagement is incongruent a strategic approach is applied to overcome dissent.

Figure 1: Methodological steps of Stakeholder Engagement; source: Own elaboration.

The comparison between the answers at the abstract level with those at the concrete level provides insights of whether a stakeholder has deeply entrenched negative (or positive) attitudes and whether it is at all feasible to seek to shift negative attitudes and convince them to take a more supportive or neutral stand. Stakeholders entrenched in negative attitudes at both levels are prone to resist changing their perspective as these views are often rooted in moral or emotional conviction rather than rational consideration (Haidt, 2012). Especially under an approach that aims at making best use of

limited resources (both in terms of time and personnel) it is most promising to focus on stakeholders whose attitudes are not entrenched in a specific position.

The consequential final step is to formulate compensatory measures in particular to those stakeholders with an "open" attitude. Therefore, **Stakeholder Analysis: Part III** focusses on **compensatory measures** using four interview questions; these are (i) technical measures to reduce the impact of wind turbines, (ii) financial participation, and (iii) participation in the decision-making process, all designed to shift stakeholders' position from neutral or opposing to support (Cowell et al., 2011).

2.2 Relation Between Stakeholder Network Analysis (SNA) and Methodological Framework

Integrating social network analysis (SNA) with our methodological framework helps to understand the dynamics of the entire network to ensure more effective and inclusive engagement strategies. Social network analysis examines the social structures and relationships among various actors to understand their interests, influence, and position in the network (Freeman, 2004). Consolidating the principles of SNA and methodological framework facilitates to visualise key characteristics of the stakeholder (stakeholder class, relationships, diversity of the network, reach, etc.). SNA has become a critical tool for examining community relationships in social sciences and economics. Recent advancements in information and communication technology (ICT) have significantly enhanced the graphical representation of networks through SNA, expanding its application to the corporate and business domains. The modern foundations of SNA trace back to the 1930s when Jacob Moreno, a psychiatrist and psychosociologist introduced sociograms to visualize relationships and interactions within communities. This pioneering methodology provided early insights into the structural dynamics of social networks and laid the groundwork for subsequent developments in the field.

SNA is instrumental in understanding the complex relationships among various actors. For instance, mapping stakeholders in regions such as Pantelleria and Styria through graphical representation reveals network structures, including relationships, influence, reciprocity, and key actors. Key characteristics of SNA include relationships, ties, and centralization, each offering

unique perspectives on the interaction and influence dynamics within networks.

2.2.1 Relationships, Ties, and Centralization

Relationships in SNA represent connections between actors or groups portrayed as nodes in the network. These relationships can be personal or professional and vary in strength and duration. For example, a wind energy project developers' connection with a municipal building authority to seek development permits demonstrates a professional relationship.

Ties link actors in a network signifying the nature of their relationships. Ties are classified as strong or weak.

- **Strong Ties:** Characterized by mutual trust, shared views, and effective communication, these ties enhance network stability and are vital during crises or critical decision-making. For example, a strong tie between a project developer and local municipalities can foster collaboration in clean energy initiatives.
- **Weak Ties:** Defined by differing views, minimal trust, and infrequent communication. Weak ties can connect disparate groups, bringing diverse perspectives. For instance, environmental conservation groups may have weak ties with wind energy developers due to differing priorities.

Centralization reflects the concentration of power, resources and information flow within the network.

- **Centralized Networks:** These are dominated by a few key actors making them efficient for initiating projects, building consensus, and resource allocation. However, such networks are vulnerable to disruptions if key actors fail.
- **Decentralized Networks:** Power and influence are distributed among multiple actors promoting resilience and inclusivity especially during the long-term execution of projects.

Centralization metrics such as degree of centrality and betweenness centrality provide further insights into structuring network analysis.

- **Degree of Centrality:** Measures how directly connected a node is to others with high-centrality nodes being pivotal for mobilizing resources and disseminating information.

- **Betweenness Centrality:** Identifies actors positioned between groups acting as mediators or brokers to resolve conflicts and facilitate collaboration.

2.2.2 Egocentric Networks and Whole networks

The above characteristics provide a robust framework to frame a network that presents a wide range of interactions among various actors and the network structure. Primarily there are two network structures egocentric network and whole network.

- **Egocentric network:** This type of network is characterised by focusing on a single node (ego) in the network and the immediate relationship (alters) that a node has with other nodes. The individualistic nature of the network provides a clear picture of the actor positions in the network. However, the potential of presence of bias may overlook important influences outside the ego's direct network.
- **Whole network:** It provides a broader picture of the entire network rather than focusing on any specific node in the network. A holistic view of the network examines the relationships among various nodes and helps to identify relationship patterns between them.

2.3 Conducting Interviews and Guidelines for Communication

The explorative interviews particularly focus on engaging with stakeholders not as speakers but as listeners to understand their concerns, needs, and wishes for the project. Before initiating engagement with stakeholders, it is important to note the decorum of the engagement in terms of clothing attire, body language, and voice modulation. These elements contribute significantly to effective communication and engagement with the stakeholders. Before engaging with stakeholders, it is essential to reflect on some key questions:

- Why am I communicating with the stakeholders?
- How do stakeholders perceive my communication?
- What do I want from the stakeholders?

The main rationale behind open explorative questions is that the stakeholder engagement process requires a balanced approach of informing, listening, understanding, and updating stakeholders (Neil Jeffery, 2009). The key information such as purpose, scope, objective, and the expected outcome of the project should be explained to the stakeholders. Additionally,

listening to stakeholder concerns, perspectives and expectations regarding the project is crucial to gain support. It is important to have empathetic behaviour to know stakeholder's needs, wishes, and suggestions. Finally, keeping stakeholders updated about the progress, milestones, and any changes that may affect them by establishing effective communication channels such as newsletters, and emails to provide timely information about the project's progress.

3. Implementation at the pilot sites Pantelleria and Styria

The developed methodological framework is implemented in pilot sites Pantelleria (Italy) and Styria (Austria) to validate its effectiveness.

- **Pantelleria** is a small volcanic island located in the south of Sicily spread over an area of 83 km² with roughly 7000 inhabitants. A researcher from the Kelso Institute Europe visited the island from 13th May to 15th May 20224 as part of the Clean Energy for EU Island Forum. This visit provided significant insights into gathering the socio-demographic characteristics of the stakeholders. A questionnaire was designed in the island's local language (Italian) to ensure data collection accuracy. A team of two researchers conducted semi-structured interviews with stakeholders from 16th September to 20th September 2024. In total 22 participants participated in a semi-structured interview. The gathered responses were transferred into an Excel table for further analysis of the stakeholders' perception of wind energy projects in the region.
- Styria is a state in south-eastern Austria often regarded as the "Green Heart of Austria" owing to lush forests, alpine mountains, and fertile plains. Two municipalities were identified to conduct semi-structured interviews namely **Irdning** and **Aigen im Ennstal**. A questionnaire was designed in the municipality's local language to ensure data collection accuracy. A team of two researchers conducted interviews with stakeholders from 21st October to 24th October 2024. In total 22 participants participated in the semi-structured interview. The data is compiled for further analysis to check the stakeholder perception of wind energy projects in the region.

In both pilot sites, there is no existing concrete wind energy project. Therefore, for the Stakeholder Analysis Part II questionnaire, a hypothetical project consisting of three wind turbines with a capacity of 750 kW each was assumed.

3.1 Step 1: Preparatory Stakeholder Mapping

A stakeholder in an undertaking is any group or individual who can affect or is affected by the achievement of the project's objectives (Freeman and McVea, 2005). Since people or groups holding stakes within a wind project can affect the direction of implementation and the chances of success or

failure of a wind power project, it is necessary to map all of such stakeholders potentially affecting project realisation. Therefore, identifying the characteristics of relevant stakeholders regarding their influence on project implementation as well as their interest is the initial step during the stakeholder mapping. We distinguish stakeholders into three categories: (i) Core Stakeholders, (ii) Expanded Core, and (iii) Multipliers with the following characteristics (see Figure 2):

- **Core stakeholders** are the primary individuals or groups that have significant interest and influence in the success or failure of the organisation or project. The core group stakeholders mainly involve project developers, landowners, the mayor, government & regulatory authorities, utility & grid operator companies, etc. The dimension and breadth of the core stakeholders may change based on the region's project, demography, and socio-political context.
- The **Expanded Core** of stakeholders are groups or individuals who may not be directly associated with the project, but their interests, concerns and influence significantly impact the project's success. These mainly include financial institutions, cultural & heritage organisations, environmental advocacy groups, NGO's, media, etc.
- **Multipliers** refer to individuals or organisations who can amplify the impact of the project through their influence, network, and communication channel. These stakeholders can help disseminate information, advocate the project, and mobilise broader support, multiplying the project's reach and effectiveness. Multipliers mainly involve influential community leaders, priests, heads of fire brigades, educational & research institutes and social media influencers.

The resulting stakeholder map (Figure 2) provides a simplified overview of all actors in pilots Pantelleria and Syria associated with a wind power project, including a preliminary categorization of their relevant roles⁶.

⁶ Annex 1 contains a fully-fledged description of the local stakeholders in Pantelleria and Syria.

Figure 2: Stakeholder map of pilot sites; source: Own elaboration

3.2 Step 2: Exploring Stakeholders' Abstract Attitudes (Stakeholder Analysis: Part I / Part 1 of the Questionnaire)

Understanding the attitudes and perceptions of identified stakeholders provides key insights for defining their role, i.e., whether stakeholders are proponents or opponents of the project, what needs they have regarding information and participation, and how they can be involved during project implementation. We use a four-dimensional stakeholder matrix with two characteristics for each dimension to measure stakeholders' attitudes, and to facilitate the analysis of stakeholders' tendencies to support or oppose a project (see Figure 3).

Climate change	Biodiversity	Money	Future
Economy			
Perpective	Reflection	Mind	Politics
Culture			

Figure 3: Eight dimension of stakeholder analysis; source: Own elaboration.

The four dimensions each reflect a general aspect relevant for opinion formation. To ensure coherent measurements and comparability of the results we use a standardised interview questionnaire to explore key characteristics from various stakeholders related to each of these dimensions.

3.2.1 Explorative Stakeholder Analysis (Questions 1-8)

The characteristics of the four dimensions of the Stakeholder Matrix and their justification are as follows:

A. Environment

The Environment has two key characteristics, namely, climate change and biodiversity. Climate change characteristics evaluate whether stakeholders believe in the existence and significance of man-made threats to the overall well-being of planetary boundary. It emphasizes the responsibility of actors for the rising threat of climate change and the willingness to become changemakers in advancing solutions. The aim of the exploration is thus to understand whether the interviewee believes that he/she is *part of the problem* and is willing to take on a corresponding *responsibility*.

Question 1 (Q1): "Do you believe climate change is human-induced and that it is one of the biggest problems of our times?"

The attitude of stakeholders toward biodiversity has two aspects, i.e., a narrow one focussing on the local situation (population-related) and a broader one taking into account the general global situation (species-related). Stakeholders with a species-related perspective are concerned with the overall health and biodiversity of the entire ecosystem. Whereas stakeholders with a population-related perspective are expected to be concerned about the survival and well-being of individual local species. The aim of the question is to explore whether they think global change for the better may require *local sacrifice*.

Q2: "Regarding the environment do you agree that the protection of global biodiversity may require to accept worse conditions for local species?"

B. Society

In the societal dimension, two characteristics are evaluated, namely perspective and reflection. Perspective refers to the extent to which stakeholders consider and take responsibility for broader global issues rather than solely focusing on immediate surroundings. The global responsibility perspective recognizes the interconnectedness of the global problem to the local context. A solely focused perspective on local issues may risk overlooking the interconnectedness of local and global systems. It mainly reflects on being a part of the solution and changemaker in solving global problems

through local initiatives. The following question aims to highlight individual sense of agency and belief in local actions to address global challenges.

Q3: "Do you believe that our actions at the local level can make a difference to solving global problems?"

Reflection refers to the degree of self-awareness and critical thinking stakeholders apply when assessing their actions and impacts on society. Stakeholders with global responsibility and high self-awareness regularly evaluate their actions, policies, and impacts on society. These stakeholders are usually quite open to learning and change. While the stakeholders with local responsibility may lack critical evaluation of the impact of their actions and policies on society. Additionally, their conservative mindset often makes them opposed to change. Therefore, global responsibility and collective care are essential to drive social cohesion in overcoming difficulties. The question probes the idea of solidarity and the balance between individual and collective responsibility during challenging times.

Q4: "Do you agree that everyone in your local society has a common responsibility to care for each other in challenging times?"

C. Economy

The economy measures stakeholders' perceptions towards expenditure and investment in developing technology to address future problems. Progressive stakeholders invest as needed to develop technology which results in the acceleration of innovation. Conversely, conservative stakeholders seeking to avoid debt to prevent burdening future generations may delay critical technology development to address future problems and increase the potential of missed opportunities due to a slower investment pace. The solution-oriented approach may accelerate the advancement of technology while the budget-oriented approach may delay the advancement of technology. Stakeholders with a budget-oriented approach look after optimising efficiency whereas a solutions-oriented mindset emphasises the effectiveness of the technology or process. The question examines whether the approach to problem-solving in the project is solution-focused or budget-conscious.

Q5: "When faced with a project challenge, do you prioritize finding the most effective solution regardless of cost?"

The future dimension navigates the balance between proactive investment and the potential debt burden on future generations. Proactive stakeholders lean towards investing now, and prioritizing investment in solutions to address future challenges such as climate change, technological advancement, etc. While conservative stakeholders prioritize fiscal responsibility and preservation of financial stability over aggressive investment in future projects. Investment behaviour and venturesome attitude determine advancing technological solutions to cope with the risk associated with climate change. It prompts stakeholders to consider whether taking on debt is justified despite the associated risk when investing in new technologies that could bring long-term benefits. The question reflects on society's readiness to prioritize future advancement even if it means accepting the financing burden now.

Q6: "When new technological innovations are introduced, do you think that debt should be taken on (with the associated risk) to explore and implement them?"

D. Culture

The cultural aspect depicts two related characteristics, i.e., mindset and political preferences. The first question seeks to understand the capabilities and level of education to entangle intricacies involved in solving climate change issues given potential limitations in resources such as time, knowledge, or training. A higher level of education and openness to complexity enables innovative and experimental approaches to develop solutions.

Q7: "Do you feel that the problems relating to solving climate change issues are too complex and that we lack the resources (time, training, etc.) to understand them?"

The two dimensions of politics are often discussed as progressive and conservative. Progressive politics favour technological advancement and innovation by enabling policy frameworks to address future problems. In contrast, conservationist politics follow the defined and proven path and may resist to new dimension of technological advancement and business. Advocacy for radical changes and openness to progressive approach disrupt the established regime to establish a new regime. The question aims to explore political willpower and openness to support radical changes or preference for established practices in solving climate change problems.

Q8: "Do you believe that radical changes, incl. technological advancements, (as opposed to traditional methods) are necessary to preserve our habitat and wellbeing?"

3.2.2 Visualisation of Stakeholder Attitudes via a Miro Board

Accompanying the stakeholder mapping and interviews, a Miro board was designed to capture the stakeholder analysis as illustrated in the following visuals. In Figure 4, the mapping is organised in three concentric circles showing multipliers in the outer shell, an expanded core of stakeholders in the middle layer, and core stakeholders in the centre.

Figure 4: Stakeholder groups

In Figure 5, the questions to the interviewees are shown as they relate to the four dimensions: environment, society, economy, and culture.

Figure 5: Interview analysis map

The third square box is used to translate the answers to the key characteristics of the four dimensions into spatial dimensions to easier grasp the tendency of the stakeholders (support, none, resist), as in Figure 6. The colours of each box represent the four dimensions: environment (green), society (blue), economy (purple) and culture (pink), and depending on the answer

given to the respective questions a specific box is highlighted for each dimension (Figure 5c).

Figure 6: Stakeholder positioning

If all the key characteristics appear towards the outmost corner of the square box, then the stakeholders are broad-minded and open. It represents that the stakeholder tends to support the project. If all the key characteristics appear towards the centre of the square box, then the stakeholders are entrenched in their attitudes and resistant to change. It represents that the stakeholder tends to resist the project. In the other case, where all the key characteristics are neither in the outermost corner nor towards the centre of the square box then the stakeholder has no outspoken tendency.

The main output of the visualisation of the responses to the explorative questions of the questionnaire (Part I, Qs 1–8) via the Miro Board is to measure the tendency to support, resist, or to take a less outspoken stance. A general perspective is assumed during this part of the stakeholder analysis. This explorative assessment is the basis for the successive stakeholder engagement, a task that goes one layer further to engage, moderate, and mitigate resistance and conflict of the stakeholder from a project-specific perspective.

3.3 Step 3: Exploring Stakeholders' Abstract Attitudes (Stakeholder Analysis: Part II / Part 2 of the Questionnaire)

Four resulting key dimensions facilitate the achievement of comprehensive stakeholder engagement: (i) knowledge reflects the level of understanding for energy transition, (ii) need for information reflects if stakeholders have enough project information, (iii) emotions reflect on the personal connec-

tion of stakeholder with land, project, etc., and (iv) need for participation assess the involvement of actors in the project in terms of finance, decision making process, etc. to raise the acceptance.

The above questions not only guide to break the ice but enhance effective engagement with the stakeholders. Additionally, some psychological factors are involved while communicating with the stakeholder such as emotions, anger, fear, fear of missing out (FOMO), etc. Thus, it's paramount to consider these factors to avoid unexpected results from engagement with the stakeholders. Also, the right moment to communicate with the stakeholders is crucial for the project's success. Engaging with stakeholders too early or too late may cause delay, significant loss, or project failure. The following guiding questions help in dialogue creation with stakeholders on four key dimensions (see Figure 7). All four dimensions help to identify stakeholder positions such as support, resistance, and neutral.

Knowledge	Information Needs	Emotions	Participation Needs
What challenges do you currently perceive? What do you know about energy transition? What do you know about wind turbine? 			

Figure 7: Guiding questions for stakeholder engagement; source: Own elaboration

The four dimensions facilitate the identification of a suitable approach to communicate with stakeholders.

Knowledge															
No	Little	Medium	High	No	Little	Medium	High	No	Little	Medium	High	No	Little	Medium	High

Figure 8: Four dimensions of stakeholder engagement; source: Own elaboration.

In addition, four indicators are used for each of the dimensions: no, little, medium, and high, to decide the approach required to communicate with the stakeholder (Figure 8). The recurrence of darker pink in four dimensions is likely to cause opposition to the project and requires strategic intervention to address stakeholders' concerns. In contrast, the recurrence of darker

green colour in four dimensions represents a tendency to support the project.

A. Knowledge

Knowledge and understanding of the project may vary based on the stakeholder type. For instance, a project developer is often highly knowledgeable about the project whereas a landowner might be less knowledgeable. A stakeholder's lack of knowledge of the project might lead to a variety of issues such as misunderstanding, increased resistance, ineffective decision-making, and communication breakdown. By using tailored information delivery, visual aids, clear communication, and engagement, project knowledge can be increased while raising awareness. A balanced approach must be applied while imparting project knowledge keeping the stakeholder type in mind. The project team can identify the need for targeted communication and tailored information delivery by evaluating stakeholders' familiarity with the topic. The question aims to identify the gaps in knowledge and inform strategies for better communication and stakeholder involvement.

Q9: "How much do you know about the Energy Transition in general?"

B. Information Needs

Similarly, the need for information characteristics emphasises providing the required information to meet the stakeholder demand in terms of processing approval, financing, and overall execution of the project. If a company wants to build a wind park in a Municipality and wants to get the necessary permission required to build a wind park then the government and regulatory authority require maximum information to evaluate the proposed wind park and give permission. In contrast, the extent of the information required for the local community might be less and different as compared to municipality and regulatory authorities. Understanding the varied information needs allows the project team to tailor communication strategies to ensure that each group receives the appropriate level of detail necessary for their decision-making process facilitating smoother project approval and implementation.

Q10: "Do you feel well-informed about the (hypothetical) wind energy project in the Pantelleria/Styria?"

C. Emotions

Emotional involvement in the project varies among stakeholders. For instance, landowners or people living in the vicinity of the proposed wind park might be highly emotionally attached to the land. Local communities are very conscious about conserving the culture and heritage monuments representing their identity, and this connection might impede the deployment of a wind park. Whereas project developers or financial institutions might not be highly emotionally attached to the project. When the emotional involvement is high then a strategic approach that focuses on listening, empathising, and, understanding stakeholder emotions is crucial. This helps to build trust, resolve concerns, and facilitate mutually agreeable decisions that benefit all parties involved.

Q11: "How do you feel about the (hypothetical) wind energy project in Pantelleria/Styria?"

D. Participation Needs

Participation in a project varies depending on stakeholder type but involving all stakeholders at the appropriate time is crucial for success. For stakeholders directly affected by the project such as local communities or landowners, participation is crucial for ensuring their concerns are addressed and their interests are safeguarded. For regulatory bodies or investors, participation might be important for overseeing compliance, ensuring financial sustainability, and supporting the project's long-term success. Various means of participation mechanisms such as financial and decision-making may raise acceptance of the project.

Q 12: "How important do you see your participation in the wind project?"

3.4 Step 4: Tendency Analysis of Stakeholder attitudes Part I and II

The "Tendency Analysis" is crucial to deciding where to focus limited resources when trying to convince stakeholders in a strategic approach. For stakeholders entrenched in whatever position an informative approach will be sufficient as shifting their positions is less likely that those who are still to be considered "open" in their attitude. For instance, if both in the abstract and the concrete analysis a stakeholder's attitudes are opposing this suggests an informative approach as it can be assumed that these stakeholders may resist changing their attitude. At the same time an informative approach does not hinder stakeholders who are entrenched in a negative at-

titude to process information at their own pace without involving more persuasive tactics. The informative approach is less costly and will often simply require a transparent information-sharing platform. A strategic approach in contrast will usually require listening, empathising, and engaging with stakeholders all activities which require personnel and resources. In summary, for stakeholders firmly entrenched in a negative stance, strategic engagement may have a limited impact on changing their perspective while possibly triggering unintended effects like giving project opponents a stage to negatively influence others still open. This not only incurs additional costs but can also risk delaying the project without achieving meaningful change in stakeholder attitudes.

In this step, results from Stakeholder Analysis Part I and II are compared to identify the position of the actors such as the tendency to support, to resist, and being neutral with regard to wind energy projects. To render the results from the two sections of the questionnaire (Parts I & II) comparable, we calculate an average for each. The stakeholder network and the results of the interviews are analysed quantitatively using an adjusted arithmetic score method, which calculates the average sentiment across stakeholders on a linear scale. Score ranges from 1 to 5, with:

- 1 to 2.99 indicating opposition,
- 3 to 3.99 representing a neutral stance,
- 4 to 5 reflecting support.

Nota bene: Instead of an arithmetic score reflecting the average sentiment of stakeholders on a linear scale⁷ we deviate with above adjusted score. The reason for this modification is that the questions regarding the "concrete wind power project" (Part II of the questionnaire) were only hypothetical wind power projects in the two chosen WIMBY-pilots (see Section 1, Introduction). Therefore, we assume that answers are still biased towards supporting the project. In fact, when testing different scales (adjusted, arithmetic, net promoter score⁸) we could observe this distortion.

⁷ A score from one to 2.33 indicates the leaning towards opposition and a score from 3.66 and 5 reflects a tendency to support.

⁸ The net promoter score is classified into three categories: opponents (1-1.8), neutral (1.8-4.2), and promoter (4.2-5). The NPS is calculated as the difference between the percentage of promoters and opponents offering a more dynamic measure of stakeholder

As shown in Figure 9, comparing the results from Stakeholder Analysis Part I and II reveals two possible outcomes. There can be congruency (meaning that both abstract and concrete analysis are in synch) or incongruency (meaning that differing tendencies pertain). With regard to the relationship between the abstract (Part I) and the concrete (Part II) analysis we give priority to the latter by weighing its result when the outcome is incongruent; for example if the concrete attitudes are sceptical while the abstract ones are neutral, the comparison result will be sceptical (but, of course "open", i.e., inviting strategic approach; see overview Section 2.1). The reason for this weighting stems from the NIMBY-phenomenon itself, where general agreement with climate mitigation measures is broadly expressed while, notwithstanding this abstract attitude, concrete measures are often still rejected. We assume, thus, that the attitudes towards concrete measures will typically override those versus abstract topics. With this assumption in mind, the comparison serves to devise the suitable approach, either "informative", or "strategic".

Maintaining trust by clear and continuous communication in the case of equality is essential to gain the support from various stakeholders. The informative approach, therefore, is foreseen in case of equality, to provide detailed and transparent project information to mitigate the concerns and conflict. This step prevents over-focusing on resolving every single resistance and instead aims to inform and mitigate concerns broadly. In contrast, where stakeholders' tendencies shift from support to opposition a strategic approach is required to engage with stakeholders. Such strategic approach is crucial to understand stakeholder concerns empathetically and establish a constructive dialogue to reduce resistance. This approach enables project developers to address specific concerns and collaboratively find solutions.

alignment. Unlike arithmetic scores, NPS emphasises extremes providing sharper contrast between supporters and opponents.

Figure 9: Tendency Analysis of Stakeholder's Attitudes; source: Own elaboration

3.5 Step 5: Compensatory Measures to increase acceptance (Part III of the Questionnaire)

Compensatory measures are essential instruments in altering stakeholder positions and improving the acceptance of wind energy projects. Compensatory measures include direct payment to affected communities, investment in local infrastructure, or support for public services like schools and recreational activities. An experimental study conducted for a hypothetical offshore wind energy project in Exmouth (UK) reveals that participant support is significantly higher when framed with community benefits compared to no-framing conditions (Walker et al., 2014). In a similar sense, various project ramifications and incentive options are provided to shift the stakeholder position and build a consensus for wind energy projects, such as technical measures, financial participation, and engagement in the decision-making process. An online survey involving 1,400 participants highlights the pivotal role of procedural and distributive justice in fostering consensus and active

acceptance of wind energy projects (Langer et al., 2018). Ensuring the fair and equitable distribution of benefits, fostering consensus through inclusive decision-making, and respecting local cultural heritage are critical components for accelerating the deployment of wind energy initiatives.

Using the above-mentioned example of a hypothetical wind power project we investigated stakeholder inclination for increased acceptance when offering them compensatory measures in Pantelleria and Styria: We evaluated (i) technical alternatives such as changes in turbine height, setback distances, the number of wind turbines, (ii) financial incentives (e.g., discounted energy prices and opportunities for equity acquisition); (iii) stakeholder involvement in decision-making processes, and transparent dissemination of regulatory information. These offers and incentives may influence citizens and stakeholders in the project to shift their positions. However, shifting the positions of stakeholders entrenched in negativity is highly challenging. These stakeholders often exhibit cognitive biases, mistrust, social dynamics, and emotional or identity-driven factors, all of which create significant barriers to altering their stance. Therefore, identifying and sorting out such stakeholders strategically is crucial to securing majority support and optimizing the use of available resources effectively.

A. Technical alternatives

In this section the question focuses on identifying technical modifications that stakeholders consider as critical in improving the acceptability of wind energy projects. It helps to understand how adjustments in turbine placement, noise reduction, or other operational features can address potential concerns and enhance support.

Q13: "Which of the following technical changes would increase your willingness to support wind energy projects in Pantelleria/Styria?"

- a) Change in setback distance*
- b) Change in turbine height*
- c) Change in number of wind turbines*
- d) Technical measures to avoid bird strikes*

B. Financial Participation

Question 14 emphasises the role of financial participation mechanisms in enhancing stakeholder support. By exploring preferences for models such

as profit-sharing, community funds, or direct investments, it shows how economic inclusion can motivate collaboration and acceptance.

Q14: "Which of the following financial participation mechanisms would increase your willingness to support wind energy projects in Pantelleria/Styria?"

- a) Discounted electricity/lower energy prices*
- b) Possibility to acquire shares in the project with own money (dividends/appreciation of shares)*
- c) Possibility to acquire shares in the project with credit from project (dividends/appreciation of shares)*
- d) Financial participation of the Municipality*

C. Participation in decision-making

Question 15 identifies the need of stakeholder involvement in decision making processes. It emphasizes the importance of participatory methods such as consultation panels, public forums, and transparent communication to ensure that stakeholders feel valued and included in project planning and implementation.

Q15: "Which of the following options for engagement in the decision-making processes would increase your willingness to support wind energy projects in Pantelleria/Styria?"

- a) Regular written information on the project progress*
- b) Early involvement in the project planning and siting processes (once per month/quarterly)*
- c) Involvement in the project implementation phase possibly also during construction (once per month/quarterly)*
- d) Being granted an elected representative of the municipality on the board of directors of the project (actual operation of wind park)*

D. Additional hypothesis

In the final section of the questionnaire, we discuss some additional hypotheses in order to evaluate stakeholder's attitudes more in detail and check for misunderstandings concerning Qs 13–15.

- 1) Economic incentives can effectively form coalitions that support the wind energy project (financial participation)*

- 2) *Access to financing/credit to participate in the project can increase my willingness to support the project (financing financial participation)*
- 3) *A citizen council's involvement in decision-making enhances trust and support for the project (participation in decision making)*
- 4) *Ensuring vulnerable households receive assistance increase the project's acceptance in the community (inclusion)*
- 5) *Higher compensation for those living closer to the project is a fair approach (fairness)*

3.5.1 Overview of Results for Compensatory Measures to increase acceptance in Pantelleria

For the Pantelleria pilot, the responses to Qs 13, 14, and 15 and the associated hypotheses provide insights into the possibility to influence stakeholder's attitudes by offering compensatory measures.

- With regard to technical modifications (Q13) the stakeholders consistently emphasized the importance of optimizing wind turbine placement and reducing noise to improve the acceptability of the projects. These adjustments are seen as essential for addressing potential concerns and building trust within the community.
- Regarding financial participation (Q14) the responses demonstrate a strong preference for financial strategies that ensure fair and inclusive benefit-sharing. Mechanisms ensuring financial benefits of the municipality rank first, energy supply at discounted prices ranks second, followed by direct investment opportunities for citizens financed by a loan from the project.
- Concerning participation in decision-making processes (Q15), the results highlight a clear priority for early involvement in the project planning and siting processes followed by Involvement in the project implementation phase possibly also during construction as stakeholders' choice of compensatory measure to support the project.

The analysis of the responses to the 5 hypotheses corroborates the previous results. Further we see two additional strategies for gaining stakeholder support, namely, (i) to form coalitions when providing economic incentives and (ii) to focus on inclusion and social equity, particularly by ensuring vulnerable households receive targeted assistance. Table 1 provides an overview of the answers for Pantelleria.

Table 1: Hypothesis analysis for part III of the questionnaire, Pantelleria

Code	Q13	Q14	Q15	Hypo1	Hypo2	Hypo3	Hypo4	Hypo5	YES Hypotheses
ca	b	e, f, h	i, j, k, l	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	5
Re	a, d	f, h	i, j	Y	Y				2
Re2	a	f	i		Y				1
sc	b	e	i, j			Y			1
me	a, b, d	e, h	i, j	Y		Y			2
Ag1									0
Ag2	c, d	f, g	j, k		Y		Y	Y	3
En2	a	e, g	i, j, k, l	Y	Y	Y		Y	4
to	d	e, f, g, h	i, j, k, l	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	5
Nc3	a	e, g, h	i, j, k						0
Nc2	a, b, c, d	e, g, h	i, j, l	Y		Y	Y	Y	4
Nc1	a, c, d	e, g, h	i, j, l						0
lo	c	f, g	i, j, k	Y					1
Np1	a, b, c, d	e, h	i, j, k	Y		Y		Y	3
Ps1	a	e, f, g, h	l		Y			Y	2

3.5.2 Overview of Results for Compensatory Measures to increase acceptance in Styria

For the Styria pilot, the responses to Qs 13, 14, and 15 and the associated hypothesis provide insights into the possibility to influence stakeholder's attitudes by offering compensatory measures. .

- With regard to technical modifications (Q13) the stakeholders consistently favour the technical measures to avoid bird strikes followed by the change in setback distance as their another priority to support the projects. These adjustments are seen as essential for addressing potential concerns and building trust within the community
- Regarding financial participation (Q14) the responses showcase a strong preference for financial strategies that ensure fair and inclusive benefit-sharing. Mechanisms such as energy supply at lower prices and financial benefits of the municipality are seen as their most selected priority to support the project.
- Concerning participation in decision-making processes (Q 15), the results highlight a clear priority for early involvement in the project planning and siting processes. This is followed involvement in the project implementation phase possibly also during construction while an elected representative of the municipality on the board of directors of the project cones last

The analysis of the responses to the 5 hypotheses corroborates the previous results. Further we see two additional strategies for gaining stakeholder support, namely, (i) to form coalitions when providing economic incentives and (iii) to focus on inclusion of citizen council in decision making to enhance more trust and support for the project execution. Table 2 provides an overview of the answers for Styria.

Table 2: Overview of respondents answers for part III of the questionnaire, Styria

Code	Q13	Q14	Q15	Hypo1	Hypo2	Hypo3	Hypo4	Hypo5	YES Hypotheses
En2	a, b, c, d	-	j	Y	-	-	-	-	1
Re1	-	h	j, k, l	-	-	Y	Y	-	2
Re3	b, c	e	i, j, l	-	-	Y	Y	Y	3
MuE	a, d	e	j, k	Y	-	-	-	Y	2
Lo1	b, c, d	e, f, g, h	j, k	Y	Y	-	Y	-	3
Mul1	a, d	e, h	i, j, l	Y	-	Y	-	Y	3
Mul2	a, d	e, h	i, j, k, l	Y	Y	-	Y	Y	4
Mul3	a, d	f, h	k	Y	-	Y	-	-	2
En1	a, b, c, d	-	j, k, l	Y	Y	Y	-	-	3
to	a, b, c, d	h	i, j, k, l	Y	-	Y	Y	Y	4
Re2	-	f, g, h	j, k, l	Y	Y	Y	-	Y	4
rel	-	-	i, j	Y	-	Y	Y	-	3
Sch1	-	e, f	i, j	Y	-	Y	-	-	2
Lo2	a, d	e	i, j	Y	-	Y	Y	Y	4
Ag&f	a, b, d	f	j, k, l	Y	Y	Y	-	Y	4

4. Result of the Network Analysis for Pantelleria and Styria

The structured questionnaire design enables the direct quantification of stakeholders' sentiments and facilitates comparisons across groups or individuals (see Section 3.4 "Tendency Analysis" above). When combined with the insights and subjective impressions gathered during interviews, this approach provides a realistic representation of stakeholders' current positions, significance, and actual or potential roles. For example, as we will see in detail, the municipality scores consistently within the supportive range, while actors in the power supplier group have mixed scores, highlighting the need for tailored engagement. Integrating the social network analysis (SNA) with the stakeholder analysis allows a visualisation that renders our insights into the relationships, roles, and influence of stakeholders in Pantelleria and Styria accessible to the reader. The analysis identifies key characteristics of these networks and suggests strategies for engagement and decision-making.

4.1 Network Characteristics

Connecting Lines (Edges): The edges between nodes represent the ties or relationships among stakeholders, providing insight into how information and resources flow within the network. Two types of edges are used: unidirectional lines, which indicate one-way relationships such as influence or opinion-making, and bidirectional lines, which signify mutual interactions and reciprocal influence. For example, residents in Pantelleria share a unidirectional relationship with the national park, reflecting a one-sided flow of opinions, whereas the national park and conservation associations exhibit a bidirectional relationship, symbolizing mutual collaboration and shared perspectives. The thickness of these lines indicates the strength of the relationship, with thicker lines denoting stronger connections that carry significant weight in decision-making or opinion formation.

Node Colours: Colours are used to classify stakeholders based on their stance toward the wind energy project. Green represents stakeholders who actively support the project, yellow highlights those with a neutral or undecided position, and red identifies opponents. This color-coding simplifies the identification of potential allies, undecided actors to engage, and opposition to address strategically.

Node Shapes: Geometric shapes differentiate stakeholder groups based on their roles and influence. Triangles represent core stakeholders who are directly involved in critical decision-making processes, such as municipalities and project developers, or can exercise a particular influence during the development of the project, like environment protection institutions or landowners. Rectangles denote the expanded core of stakeholders, who may not be directly involved in decision-making but exert significant influence or interest, such as conservation associations or entrepreneurs. Circles identify multipliers, actors who amplify information and shape public opinion, such as schools, citizens, and cultural associations. This classification helps to visualize the varying levels of stakeholder involvement and prioritize engagement strategies accordingly.

Borders: The presence or absence of borders around shapes indicates the rigidity of a stakeholder's stance. Stakeholders with borders around their shapes are entrenched in a position, whether supportive or opposing, and are less likely to change. For example, the national park administrator is rep-

resented with a border, reflecting their firm opposition to the project. Conversely, stakeholders without borders are more flexible and open to influence, making them key targets for engagement efforts.

4.2 Key Insights for Pantelleria

4.2.1 Identification of stakeholder groups

The **core group** consists of stakeholders whose involvement is critical to the project's success. In this analysis, it includes stakeholders categorized under specific identifiers: municipality (mu), power supplier (ps), landowners (lo). They have a direct and substantial influence on the project's planning, implementation and outcomes. The group includes two stakeholders affiliated with municipal roles (mu1, mu2), two from the power supplier (ps1 and ps2), two from the national park (np1, np2) and a landowner (lo), highlighting their critical roles in land management and decision-making.

The **expanded group** includes stakeholders from related sectors that, while not directly essential to the project, significantly affect or are affected by its outcomes. This group encompasses diverse categories, including nature conservation groups (nc1, nc2, nc3), entrepreneurs (en1, en2, en3), tourism associations (to), and agricultural stakeholders (ag1, ag2).

The **multiplicators** act as connectors and amplifiers within the network, facilitating the flow of information and expanding the project's influence across the broader community. In this analysis, they include stakeholders categorized under schools (sch), media (me), residents (re).

Figure 10: Network Analysis for Pantelleria

4.2.2 General and concrete opinions of the stakeholders

Core stakeholders, such as the municipality (mu1 and mu2) and the national park (np1 and np2), are pivotal in decision-making processes due to their high centrality. Both actors from the municipality, for instance, are strong supporters of the project and are engaged in bidirectional relationships with the national park actors. However, the national park exhibits a split stance: while the director (np1) shows potential for strategic engagement, the park administrator (np2) is firmly opposed, emphasizing nature conservation concerns. This divergence within the national park highlights the need for a tailored approach when engaging with such influential entities.

The relationships between stakeholders also reveal complex patterns of influence. For example, the power supplier group (ps1 and ps2) presents contrasting dynamics: one actor (ps2) firmly opposes the project, while the other (ps1) is currently neutral but engaged in key bidirectional relationships with both the national park and the municipality. These interactions suggest opportunities to influence undecided actors through collaborative dialogue, leveraging their connections to other key stakeholders.

The expanded stakeholder group includes entities such as nature conservation associations (nc1 and nc2), entrepreneurs (en1, en2), and a tourism organization representative (to). Many of these actors are undecided about their stance on the project, reflecting the hypothetical nature of the wind energy initiative and a lack of detailed information. For instance, an architect and planning expert within the nature conservation (nc3) association exhibits a neutral position but maintains unidirectional links with the municipality, suggesting that targeted information-sharing could positively shift their perspective. On the other hand, some stakeholders, such as a shopkeeper in the entrepreneur group (en1), are firmly opposed to the project and require an informative approach to address their concerns.

Multipliers, including citizens, media, schools, and cultural associations, have less direct involvement in decision-making but play a significant role in shaping opinions. Their influence, although indirect, can help amplify support or opposition within the broader community. While their ties to other stakeholders are generally weaker, their potential for opinion formation suggests that consistent engagement and information dissemination could enhance their alignment with the project.

4.2.3 Strategic stakeholder engagement

With respect to the core group, the network analysis highlights the strategic need to focus on the municipality (mu1 and mu2), the landowner (lo) and the first representative of the national park (np1) who, unlike the other representative (np2) is still undecided and can be convinced more easily.

With respect to the expanded core, most actors have a neutral opinion towards the projects. Only one entrepreneur (en1) and one nature conversation representative (nc2) are against the project. It would strategically make most sense to thus focus on the residual stakeholders, including nc1 and nc3, en2 and en3, to and ag1 and ag2.

With respect to the multipliers, one crucial stakeholder against the project is media (me). Given their significant role in influencing attitudes among residents, it makes sense to explore whether their entrenched position against the project can be changed in any way.

4.3 Key insights from the social network analysis: Styria

4.3.1 Identification of stakeholder groups

The **core group** comprises stakeholders from key sectors critical to the project's success. In our analysis, it includes eight individual stakeholders categorised under four distinct identifiers (IDs): municipality (mu), landowners (lo), power supplier (ps) and project developer (pd). Among these, four individual stakeholders are affiliated with the two municipalities Irndings-Donnersbachtal ad Aigen im Ennstal (mul1, mul2, mul3, and muE), and two are landowners (lo1 and lo2).

The **expanded core** includes stakeholders from adjacent sectors that, while not essential for the project's success, significantly influence or are influenced by it. This group consists of six individual stakeholders categorised under five distinct identifiers (IDs): nature conservation associations (nc), tourism associations (to), agricultural and forestry stakeholders (ag&f), the regional government (rgov) and entrepreneurs (en). Among these, two stakeholders act as entrepreneurs (en1, en2).

Figure 11: Network Analysis for Styria

The **multiplicators** serve as connectors and disseminators of information, amplifying the network's reach and influence. In our analysis, they include seven stakeholders categorised under three distinct identifiers (IDs): religious entities (rel), schools (sch), and residents (re). These include one

stakeholder affiliated with a religious entity (rel), three school representatives (sch1, sch2, sch3) and three residents (re1, re2, re3).

4.3.2 General and concrete opinions of the stakeholders

The stakeholder network in Styria reveals a complex interplay of influence, interest, and relationships with significant implications for the wind energy project's success:

With respect to the core stakeholders, more generally, the municipality (mu) plays a pivotal role in project planning, leveraging its administrative authority and regulatory competence. Similarly, the willingness of at least one landowner (lo) to lease their land directly impacts the project's feasibility. Furthermore, the project's realisation relies on two additional contributions: the power supplier's (ps) provision of grid connectivity and the project developer's (pd) initiative, forming the backbone of the wind farm's execution. The concrete network analysis highlights the municipality's internal dynamics. Mu1 (the head of the office at Irdning-Donnersbachtal) maintains close ties with mu2 (the head of the building authority department), whose control over land-use policies is crucial for project approval. Mu3 (the vice mayor), an experienced and charismatic figure, holds a unique position of influence over mu1 and mu3. Together with muE (the head of office in Aigen im Ennstal), their geographic and administrative proximity fosters potential for collaborative efforts. Landowners also play a crucial role. Lo1 demonstrates proactive interest in renewable energy, evidenced by existing solar PV installations. Given the vast land lo1 owns, this stakeholder has already been approached by a project developer (pd). Lo2, a regional pioneer, shows proactive interest towards renewable energy as well, having already adopted a small wind turbine (7kW), solar PV (13.5kW) and an energy storage system (6kW). Collaboration between municipal actors and these landowners is essential for identifying suitable land for the project.

With respect to the expanded stakeholders, more generally, nature conservation associations (nc) emphasise biodiversity and sustainable practices, while tourism associations (to) highlight the project's impact on regional attractiveness. Agricultural and forestry stakeholders (ag&f) focus on land-use and resource management, while the regional government (rgov) ensures alignment with overarching policy frameworks. Entrepreneurs (en) provide investment potential but may challenge the project by prioritizing

other profit-driven objectives. In our concrete analysis, the nature conservation association (nc), affiliated with the Styrian Greens, demonstrates a positive relationship with municipal representatives (mul1 – mul3), potentially fostering alignment on sustainability goals.

The hotel owner (en1) is a renewable energy pioneer, promoting environmental awareness and implementing advanced technologies like heat pumps. Being a charismatic figure, the hotel owners has also coined the term “climate emergency” (German: “Klimanotstand”), which has become a media-effective description of the need to urgently tackle the climate crisis in Austria. However, this individual is sceptical of wind energy, advocating for reduced economic growth as a solution before constructing wind turbines in the region. Similarly, a bookshop owner (ec2) is a vocal opponent of wind energy, interacting regularly with young parents in the community (e.g., lo1), which could influence public sentiment. The agricultural and forestry stakeholder (ag&f) acts as an opinion-maker, engaging with the community through activities like selling Christmas trees and leveraging familial ties to neighbouring municipalities (e.g., son is working for the public authority). The regional government advisor (rgov), with a focus on wildlife ecology, holds hierarchical authority over municipal representatives (mul1-mul3, muE), potentially influencing their stance on wind energy projects.

With respect to the multipliers, more generally, religious entities (rel) bring a cultural and ethical dimension to the network, emphasising moral alignment. Schools (sch), in turn, provide scientific and educational authority, shaping resident's understanding, while residents (re) connect to the community, fostering engagement. In our concrete network analysis, the guardian at the religious entity (rel), a monastery, emerges as a charismatic figure with strong community ties, actively engaging in renewable energy initiatives. The religious entity has installed large PV panels on its land, regularly using a web-application to monitor the energy production and consumption of the monastery. To secure the necessary administrative permit, the religious entity has maintained close communication with municipal representatives (mul1-mul3), possibly raising their awareness of the need to contribute to the energy transition on a larger level. The school director (sch1) manages two educational buildings equipped with PV-panels on their roofs. To finance the panels, the school offered residents and other interested stakeholders the opportunity to acquire shares in the PV-project.

This, again, could have played and still pay an influential role in shaping opinions on renewable energy.

One of the residents interviewed, re3, stands out given the multiple positions the individual holds (voluntary treasurer of the municipality, firefighter, and hunter), thus amplifying the individual's potential for opinion-shaping within the community. Notably, this resident (re3) and the landowner (lo1) share hunting as a common interest, providing another layer of connection within the network.

4.3.3 Strategic stakeholder engagement

With respect to the core group, the network analysis highlights the strategic need to focus on the vice mayor (mul3), the head of office in Aigen im Ennstal (muE) and the landowner who has been approached by a wind park developer in the past (lo1). All three are currently undecided but, in their roles, are crucial for the project's success. Rather than expending limited resources on the head of office (mul1) and the head of the building authority department (mul2), who have a negative stance towards the project, it is more effective to concentrate efforts on those who can be persuaded with minimal effort. The second landowner (lo2), already convinced of the benefits of wind energy, can provide additional support in this endeavour.

With respect to the expanded core, the nature conservation association (nc) has a positive stance towards wind energy and could help sway the representative of the tourism association (to), who is still undecided, as well as the regional government representative (rgov), who also remains neutral. Focusing on these three groups may yield better results than attempting to change the positions of the agricultural and forestry stakeholder (ag&f) and the two entrepreneurs (en1, en2), who are negatively inclined towards the project.

Focusing on the multipliers, the religious entity (rel), the school director (sch1), and the community-involved resident (re3) could play pivotal roles in strengthening public opinion in favour of the wind energy project. Their influential positions and community ties make them valuable allies in building broader support.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Wind power has great potential to underpin achieving clean energy targets but opposition from various stakeholders has and will continue to delay or even hinder its deployment. Therefore, effective stakeholder engagement is crucial to overcome resistance and increase acceptance deploying an engagement strategy that enhances trust, transparency, and open communication with all local stakeholders. Here, to make best use of limited resources like time, personnel and expertise, an approach should focus on those stakeholders that are yet undecided in their attitudes towards the concerning wind project and be tailored specifically to their needs and capabilities. Prerequisite to above approach is investigating stakeholders' attitudes, expectations and relations between them in an open explorative way.

Our systematic WIMBY-approach was developed from best practice of practitioners and is designed to efficiently understand stakeholders' perceptions, concerns and potential objections related to wind projects. In doing so we consider attitudes that pertain both to an abstract and a concrete level. Following the principles of network analysis, we employ a cluster analysis shedding light on local stakeholders' characteristics and attitudes towards project implementation in particular with respect to their relations with each other. Integrating the social network analysis with the stakeholder analysis allows a visualisation that renders our insights into the relationships, roles, and influence of stakeholders accessible to the reader.

The three respective steps of our methodology are: a) data collection on the bases of desk-based literature research; b) semi-structured interviews with the main stakeholders conducted at the implementation sites; and c) network analysis on the basis of a comprehensive digest of the semi-structured interviews. The interview-based approach allows to verify the identification, mapping and clustering of all relevant stakeholders while assessing their characteristics and attitudes towards project implementation and their respective relation to each other. An advantage of this interactive process is its potential to address concerns of stakeholders who are in opposition to wind power projects and gain their support in a targeted manner. This includes exploring compensatory measures to mitigate antagonising local stakeholders of wind projects, increase their acceptance and gain their support for wind energy initiatives.

The network analysis of Pantelleria and Styria underline the importance of individuals on a wind energy project's success and the variety of key actors, depending on the region. While, in Pantelleria, people affiliated with the national park and the media play a significant role in opinion-shaping, in Styria, it is renewable energy pioneers who influence public opinion.

From above analysis of two - albeit hypothetical - wind projects we conclude that with rare exceptions all local stakeholders are sympathetic to compensatory offers potentially increasing their acceptance. We can distinguish three groups of offers, namely, (i) technical modifications, (ii) financial participation, and (iii) participation in decision-making. All options were ranking similarly in importance and need to be considered in a negotiating process. We summarise the options as follows:

- (i) Technical modifications, like changes in turbine height, setback distances, the number of wind turbines.
- (ii) Financial participation, like discounted energy prices and opportunities for equity acquisition.
- (iii) Participation in decision-making, i.e., stakeholder involvement in decision-making processes.

All three types of compensatory offers need to be based on transparent and regular dissemination of project information. While such offers and incentives may influence stakeholders' attitude to project implementation, shifting the positions of stakeholders entrenched in a negative attitude is challenging. These stakeholders often exhibit cognitive biases, mistrust, social dynamics, and emotional or identity-driven factors, all of which create significant barriers to altering their stance. Therefore, identifying and sorting out such stakeholders strategically is crucial to securing majority support and optimizing the use of available resources effectively.

An overview of existing key regulatory approaches to financial participation and compensation schemes is provided in deliverable 2.10.

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7. ANNEX

7.1 A. Stakeholder mapping for the Pantelleria Pilot

Pantelleria, a small volcanic Italian island is located 110 km South of Sicily, in the centre of the Sicilian Channel extending over an area of 83 km² with a population of approx. 7,700 inhabitants. It has typical warm Mediterranean weather, tempered by strong marine wind and characterized by a high frequency of sea waves. This combination of natural forces makes the island perfectly suitable for the design of a renewable energy supply system. The electricity distribution network is disconnected from the European transmission grid and powered by several diesel generators with a combined capacity of 22 MW; diesel is imported from the mainland at high environmental and economic cost.

Existing RE installations: Today more than 1,100 kWp of PV panels are installed on Pantelleria. Furthermore, a 30kW horizontal axis wind turbine – although decommissioned – still exists on Pantelleria and large exploitation of wind energy is one of the pillars of the Clean Energy Transition Agenda, under deployment on the island with the support of the Clean Energy for EU Islands Secretariat. Most RE plants have been installed in recent years, and further development is expected in the next few years, thanks to recently introduced national incentive policies for small non-interconnected islands. Under the guidance of the Clean Energy for EU Islands Secretariat, Pantelleria has published its Clean Energy Transition Agenda in October 2020. A major share of the energy demand must be attributed to the desalters (1,200 kW p.a.), producing all the freshwater needed by the inhabitants and numerous holidaymakers.

Planned investments in RE and smart mobility (2022) – The local DSO and the main electricity producer (SMEDE) have built and connected a new 500 kWp PV plant in 2021. The deployment of electric buses for public transportation on Pantelleria island is foreseen with an earmarked budget from the Municipality of Pantelleria and the National Park for the procurement of 5 electric buses in 2023/2024 (+3 municipal e-busses). To compensate for the additional electricity that is going to be consumed by the electric buses, the National Park has received additional funds to install approx. 200 kWp rooftop PV installations. The municipality received the funding for a fifth electric bus, together with the PV plant needed to cover its energy demand.

The local desalination plants have potential for deferrable loads as temporal synchronicity between production and consumption is not fully required. The desalters produce sweet water that is stored in a batch of tanks throughout the territory and, when needed, is pumped to the final users.

To engage citizens in demand side management schemes, i.e., the promotion of self-consumption depending on production, **a number of private residential users (at least 100) is equipped with second generation smart meters.** The additional benefits on grid flexibility deriving from the implementation of demand-side management strategies at the household's scale are thus assessed on top of other measures tested at the grid scale (grid-scale energy storage systems and large-scale deferrable loads such as water desalination plants).

a) Public sector

Municipality of Pantelleria – The Municipality covers the 100% of the island surface area and is part of the Libero Consorzio di Trapani (Trapani province). The Municipality is in a good economic state and, also because of the great distance from the mainland, it has a solid administrative structure, able to manage all public services for citizens; there is also a highly qualified technical office. The island, has schools of all levels of education, an international airport and a hospital. The current administration strongly believes in energy transition and distributed power plants, but also in citizens co-ownership of centralized power plants.

National Park Island of Pantelleria – The Island of Pantelleria National Park is a protected natural area of national interest that was established in 2016, following a fire that took place on the island, and is the first and only National Park in Sicily. The managing body of the national park is a public entity dependent on the Ministry of the Environment. Its surface is 6,560 ha, equal to 78% of the total surface of the island; the territory is divided into 3 zones with different levels of anthropization. The aim of the Park is to preserve the ecosystem of the island and its traditional anthropic activities; the Statute of the Authority presents the objective to make these anthropic activities sustainable, also through the supply of energy from renewable sources, in harmony with nature and landscape. The administration of the National Park has repeatedly and publicly expressed itself in favor of power generation from renewable sources, even by means of wind turbines. The Park has recently received the allocation of funds from the Ministry for the purchase of 5 electric

buses and the installation of a photovoltaic system to produce the energy they consume on an annual basis.

Sicily Region – The Region has a considerable importance in the energy transition of Pantelleria, all the more so because it is a region with an autonomous statute. In particular, the landscape and cultural heritage superintendence depends on the Region, and not on the national Ministry. The regional energy plan identifies Pantelleria as a pilot island for the energy transition. **However, until now D.P.REG. 10/0/2017 (regional decree) has established that the installation of wind turbines above 20 kW should be prohibited in all areas of environmental protection on Sicilian soil.** Pantelleria is entirely part of an Important Bird and Biodiversity Areas (IBA), and therefore the regional law, designed to protect the Sicilian landscape and avoid the installation of wind turbines in area of high landscape value, effectively prevents the installation of wind turbines in all the territory of the island. The local administrations have been in contact with the Region since some months to try eliminating this constraint and to be able to analyze the proposed wind energy projects on a case by case basis; in particular, an abandoned industrial area of really low landscape value in the north-west part of the island has been identified for a possible future installation of wind turbines.

b) Businesses

S.MED.E. S.p.A. – With a capitalization of EUR 3.8 mln. the small electricity company operates the electricity distribution network (DSO) and owns the diesel power plant. The Pantelleria power plant, which feeds a system isolated from the rest of the national grid, was excluded from nationalisation in 1962 and has always been totally managed by SMEDE S.p.A. The company receives an economic support of approx. EUR 9.7 mln. from the authority for the regulation of the energy networks, through an equalisation mechanism: this sum serves to cover the higher costs deriving from the production of energy through diesel generators and from the complex management of the isolated electric system. The company has recently built a 500 kWp photovoltaic system, the largest existing on the island, and is ready to install more PV in the coming months and years. It favours distributed generation, but considers it essential to have a centralized production plant – also from renewable sources – to allow an effective management of the grid. **SO.FI.P.**

S.p.A. is the holding company of S.MED.E. S.p.A., and owns the minor electricity companies operating on two other minor Sicilian islands. It is an ESCo, and – among other things – manages the desalination plants on the island of Pantelleria.

Consortium for the Protection and Valorisation of DOC wines of the Island of Pantelleria – The consortium has 7 bottlers and winemakers and over 300 winemaking members. Although not all the wineries are part of the consortium, it is the largest and only group of wine operators on the island.

Agricultural cooperative capers producers – The 250 producer members stock approximately 1,500 quintals of capers every year, which are marketed as a single unit. Not all the producers are part of the cooperative, which however collects the vast majority of producers.

c) Civil society organizations

Most civil society organizations are cultural and recreational associations, which – especially in winter – animate the cultural life of the island. Their role can be important for the communication phase; however, there are other associations and organisations that can play a more prominent role in the energy transition on Pantelleria.

Citizens who own the 30 kW wind turbine – In 2014 four citizens founded a civil law partnership for installing a 30 kW wind turbine in “Località Arenella” (north-west part of the island) which, however, has been decommissioned.

Travel & Island Consortium – The consortium that brings together the major tourist facilities on the island and operators in the sector. It is responsible for the promotion of the island and receives reservations for the associated tourist facilities.

Pro loco Pantelleria – A recently established association with similar objectives to those of the consortium described above.

Recreational clubs – There are 15 recreational clubs, scattered throughout the island, which are the main social gathering places during the winter.

Pantelleria Internet Cultural Association – The association, thanks to the contributions of readers, produces the main daily newspaper of the island, which is sent by email to all members.

RESILEA APS – A social promotion association that is committed to sustainability and resilience.

7.2 Annex: Stakeholder mapping for the Styria Pilot

Styria has a population of approximately 1.3 million residents, with a nearly equal distribution between men and women. This makes it the fourth most populous federal state in Austria. The average age of the population is 44.6 years and is steadily increasing. Known as the "Green Heart of Austria," the region is renowned for its forests and natural landscape. Forests cover 58% of the total area, followed by agriculture (18%), and the Alpine mountain range (16%).

Energy outlook in Austria – The country is self-reliant to meet its energy demand. Domestic production accounts for 87.6% in the total primary energy production. The country's energy production is highly dominated by bioenergy (46.1%), hydro-electric power (26.6%) and rest of energy production by others in 2023. Wind energy account only 5.3% in the total energy production whereas solar PV accounts for 4%. Burgenland (35.2%) and lower Austria (56.1%) accounts for more than 90% of electricity production from wind in 2022. Styria accounts only 7.1% electricity production from wind in 2022. The wind turbines are highly concentrated in Burgenland and lower Austria. Styria accounts ~20% of the electricity production from solar PV in the country. Austria needs to install a gigawatt wind capacity year on year from 2025 in order to achieve its 2030 decarbonisation target.

Energy outlook in Styria – The primary energy production in the region is highly dominated by biomass accounting two third of the total energy production followed by 17.4% from hydro-electric power. Wind energy accounted only 2.7% and solar PV 3.9% in primary energy production in 2022. There are total 118 wind turbines installed in the state with a capacity of 306.55 MW. The region accounts for 16.7% of the total GHG emission in Austria.

Existing RE installations – The definition of "Green Heart of Austria" is also reflected in Styria's primary energy production. Like its forest coverage, which stands at 58%, biomass accounts for the largest share of primary energy production at nearly 65%. Hydropower follows in second place with over 22%, underscoring its importance to the region. The use of ambient heat currently accounts for only 5.3%, though it has steadily increased in recent years. A similar trend is observed with wind (2.8%) and photovoltaics (2.2%),

which, despite their relatively small absolute contributions, have shown significant growth rates. Additionally, burnable waste contributes 2.5% to the region's primary energy production.

Planned investments in RE and smart mobility (2022) – The Energie Steiermark AG (Energy Styria Stock Company), established as the umbrella organisation for the federal state of Styria in 1996, is a leading energy and service company in the region. Between 2015 and 2021, the company invested an average of EUR 150.3 million per year, with further significant increases in recent years: EUR 217.4 million in 2022 and EUR 221.3 million in 2023. For 2024, investments of EUR 316 million are planned. By 2030, the company aims to integrate 2,000 MW of photovoltaic and 800 MW of wind energy into the grid operated by Energienetze Steiermark (Energy Grids Styria), a subsidiary of Energie Steiermark AG, further solidifying its role in advancing Styria's renewable energy transition.

The WIMBY pilot comprises of three municipalities, namely, Aigen im Ennstal, Stein an der Enns and Irdning:

Aigen im Ennstal (district Irdning-Donnersbachtal)

The municipality is located in the Enns Valley in the Austrian state of Styria. The population of the region is around 2,700 with an equal proportion of men and women. Manufacturing of goods, trades, public administration, health & social services, and building sector provide more than 60% of the employment in the region. The average gross salary earned by people living in the region is EUR 42,662 less than average gross salary of the Austria (EUR 46,991). A considerable population is literate with the compulsory school. The region's natural landscape attracts tourists which shows a continuous inflow of tourists throughout the year. However, the tourist inflow is quite high from June to September.

Politics – The current mayor is from Österreichische Volkspartei (ÖVP – Austrian Peoples Party). The ÖVP currently hold 8 seats in the local council, followed by Gemeinsam für Aigen (GEFA – Together for Aigen) with 4 seats and the Social Democratic Party (SPÖ – Sozialdemokratische Partei Österreichs) with 3 seats. The data is based on the last local council election that took place in June 2020; the next election will take place in 2025. The ÖVP is characterised as a Christian democratic and conservative party whereas the SPÖ advocates for social democracy and progressive policies. The GEFA is a

citizen-led party which, according to its website, does not follow party interests.

Stein an der Enns (district Sölk)

Stein an der Enns is a village located in the valley of the river Enns and part of the Sölk municipality. More than two third of the municipality's area is covered by forests and alps. Due to its scenic and natural landscape lot of tourist visit the place. The tourist inflow is spread across the year with high inflow in February, June, July, August and September. The population of the municipality is around EUR 1,489 in 2024 with equivalent proportion of men and female. The population is relative aged with half of the population above the age of 45. The average annual gross salary in the municipality is EUR 38,856 which much lower than the national average of EUR 46,491. Building, manufacturing of goods, trade and transportation sector provide more than half the employment in the region.

Politics – The current mayor is a member of the ÖVP. This party enjoys strong backing in the local council (8 seats), followed by the Freedom Party of Austria (FPÖ – Freiheitliche Partei Österreichs) with 2 seats and the SPÖ (1 seat). The FPÖ is known for its far-right populist and national conservative stance.

Irdning (district Irdning-Donnersbachtal)

Irdning, located in the Enns Valley, is part of the municipality of Irdning-Donnersbachtal in Styria. The population of Irdning is approximately 2,700, with a nearly equal distribution of men and women. The local economy is diverse, with key employment sectors including agriculture, public services, tourism, and trade. The average annual gross salary is EUR 41,500, slightly below the national average of EUR 46,991, reflecting the rural and tourism-oriented nature of the economy. The region is known for its natural landscapes, attracting tourists year-round, with peak visits in the summer and winter months.

Politics – The current mayor of Irdning-Donnersbachtal (Irdning itself does not have a mayor) is a member of the ÖVP. This party most seats in the local council (14), followed by the FPÖ (3), the SPÖ (2) and the Greens (2).

